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Optimization of the enzymatic synthesis of structured triacylglycerols rich in docosahexaenoic acid at *sn*-2 position by acidolysis of *Aurantiochytrium limacinum* SR21 oil and caprylic acid using Response Surface Methodology.

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31 Abstract

32

33 *Aurantiochytrium limacinum SR21* is a promising source of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) for human
34 consumption as dietary supplement, replacing traditional fish oil. This work deals with the production of
35 structured triacylglycerols (STAGs) with caprylic acid (CA) located at *sn*-1,3 positions and DHA at *sn*-2
36 position of the glycerol molecule. This process is conducted by acidolysis of CA and *A. limacinum SR21*
37 oil catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM. A central composite design with response surface
38 was used to optimize the reaction temperature and the intensity of treatment (IOT). Statistical models
39 adequately describe the reaction behavior ($R^2 > 0.91$). The optimal temperature values were 37 °C for both
40 lipases. Additionally, IOTs of 9.02 and 7.87 g lipase \times h/g TAG were established for TL- IM and RM-IM,
41 respectively. The reaction was scaled up by multiplying the amounts of *A. limacinum* oil, CA, lipase, and
42 hexane (used as reaction medium) by a factor of 20 while maintaining the IOTs constant. TL-IM showed a
43 better performance to catalyze the acidolysis reaction than RM-IM, achieving 40.8 mol% of total CA
44 incorporated (91.2% of total incorporated at *sn*-1,3 positions), while the palmitic acid (PA) content at *sn*-
45 1,3 positions decreased from 77.3 to 20.4 mol%. DHA represented 45.5 mol% of fatty acids at *sn*-2 position
46 and 15.7 mol% of fatty acids at *sn*-1,3 positions. Using RM-IM, STAGs of similar composition were
47 obtained.

48

49 **Keyword:** Structured triacylglycerol, docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), *Aurantiochytrium limacinum SR21*,
50 enzymatic reaction, Response Surface Methodology.

51

52 Highlights:

53

54 STAGs highly rich in DHA at *sn*-2 position and CA at *sn*-1,3 positions were obtained from *A. limacinum*
55 oil.

56 STAGs with 45.5 mol% of DHA at *sn*-2 position (of fatty acids at this positions) along with 55.8 mol% of
57 CA at *sn*-1,3 positions (of fatty acids at these positions) were obtained.

58 PA content at *sn*-1,3 positions decreased from 77.3 to 20.4 mol% by means of acidolysis reactions.

59 RSM satisfactorily describes enzymatic acidolysis with coefficients R^2 greater than 0.90 for Lipozyme TL-
60 IM and RM-IM.

61 **Introduction**

62

63 Structured triacylglycerols (STAGs) are triacylglycerols (TAGs) that have been modified to alter their fatty
64 acid composition as well as their location in the glycerol backbone, via chemical or enzymatic means, for
65 functional or nutritional purposes (Talbot, 2015a). TAGs can be structured to satisfy essential fatty acid
66 requirements or to incorporate specific fatty acids of interest. STAGs constitute an efficient way for
67 delivering target fatty acids for nutritive or therapeutic purposes, as well as to alleviating specific diseases
68 and metabolic conditions (Wei et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2017).

69 One of the most popular STAGs is medium-long-medium STAG (MLM-STAG), which contains medium-
70 chain fatty acids (MC-FAs) at *sn*-1,3 positions of the glycerol backbone and long-chain polyunsaturated
71 fatty acids (LC-PUFAs) or essential FAs at *sn*-2 position. MLM-STAGs lead a better intestinal absorption
72 of fatty acids and influences on their metabolic fate in the organism (Gudmundsdottir et al., 2015; He et al.,
73 2018; Hita et al., 2007). MC-FAs present in human diets are quickly released from the *sn*-1,3 positions
74 under the action of preduodenal lipases (Clark et al., 1969), allowing direct absorption by the stomach
75 mucosa (Lemarié et al., 2016). MC-FAs are also easily transferred to the portal circulation and transported
76 as free FAs, since they easily enter the mitochondria independently of the carnitine transport system, as
77 opposed to LC-PUFAs (Lemarié et al., 2018). MC-FAs are used to provide energy, while the 2-MAG (with
78 the LC-PUFA) are well absorbed via the lymphatic route (Picq et al., 2013; Talbot, 2015b). According to
79 the digestive characteristic of dietary lipid, fatty acids can be absorbed when released from the TAGs
80 structures as free fatty acids or as 2-MAGs after digestive lipolysis (Michalski et al., 2013). The 2-MAGs
81 are most readily absorbed through the intestinal mucosa and are used directly for the resynthesis of TAGs
82 or phospholipids (PLs; important components of the brain cell membrane). At this respect, Jin et al., (2020)
83 show how the positional arrangement of the LC-PUFA (docosahexaenoic acid, DHA, in this work) in TAG
84 and PL structures influences its pharmacological and nutritional benefits for human brain development and
85 maintenance.

86 On the other hand, saturated FAs with more than 16 carbon atoms, hydrolyzed by the digestive lipases from
87 the *sn*-1,3 positions, may form insoluble calcium soaps that precipitate in the intestinal track producing
88 hard stools, which frequently cause intestinal disorders in infants and adults (Şahin et al., 2006; Tonetto
89 and Ferreira, 2017; Wei et al., 2019). Wu et al. (2017b) reported on the state of the research regarding
90 STAG absorption in terms of clinical outcomes. The authors found that, in postsurgical and/or critically ill

91 patients, the administration of MLM-STAGs versus medium-chain/long chain TAGs (MCTAG/LCTAG)
92 physical mixtures was significantly associated with improved protein economy, better liver tolerance, and
93 a more efficient TAG elimination. Caprylic acid (CA, octanoic acid, C8:0) belongs to the class of MC-FAs,
94 and it is an abundant nutrient in coconut oil (6–10% of FAs) and in palm kernel oil (2–5% of FAs), where
95 it occupies the *sn-1,3* positions of TAGs (Fanny Lemarié et al., 2016). Several LC-PUFAs are commonly
96 used to synthesize STAGs, such as eicosapentaenoic (EPA, 20:5n3) and docosahexaenoic acids (22:6n3,
97 DHA). The latter is an essential ω 3-LC-PUFA that is necessary for the building of brain membranes, and
98 nerves and retina tissues in humans (Dunbar et al., 2014; Nagachinta and Akoh, 2013). Numerous beneficial
99 effects on human health and prevention of diseases are attributed to DHA; among them cardiovascular
100 diseases, inflammation, autoimmune diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, Alzheimer's disease and related
101 neurodegenerative disorders and cancer (Nichols et al., 2014; Spector and Kim, 2019; Sugasini et al., 2017).
102 Numerous works have been published showing the advantages to incorporate DHA and MC-FAs in the
103 same molecule. Christensen et al., (1995) compared the absorption of EPA, DHA and decanoic (DA, 10:0)
104 acids in mesenteric lymph duct-cannulated rats following intragastric administration of two oils with
105 different intramolecular TAGs structures; one oil with EPA and DHA located at the *sn-2* position and
106 decanoic acid in the *sn-1,3* positions (specific MLM-STAG) and the other oil with a random fatty acid
107 distribution. These authors concluded that specific MLM-STAGs, with EPA and DHA predominantly at
108 the *sn-2* position of the TAGs was a more readily absorbed source of EPA and DHA. Similarly, *sn-2* DHA
109 monoacylglycerol (MAG) has showed significantly higher absorption efficiency than other derivatives,
110 such as DHA diacylglycerol (DAG) and DHA-ethyl ester in rats (Banno et al., 2002; Valenzuela et al.,
111 2005). Also, Zou et al., (2021) revealed the beneficial effects of STAGs with DHA and medium chain fatty
112 acids in the same molecule for fat digestion and absorption in infants, which can increase the bioavailability
113 of DHA at the molecular level. Therefore, based on the important physiological significance of DHA for
114 infants, these authors reveal the necessity of developing structured lipids that can help to further improving
115 the bioavailability of DHA for the supplementation of infant formula.

116 In comparison to chemical methods, enzymatic methods have been widely used in preparing STAGs due
117 to their milder reaction conditions, higher catalytic specificity, no toxicity, less oxidation, and easier
118 separation of catalyst (He et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2016). Moreover, lipases are capable of incorporating
119 fatty acids at specific positions in the glycerol backbone, and thereby, producing more specifically tailored
120 lipids with specific functional properties or bioavailability (Korma et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2017; Wei et al.,

121 2019). In this regards, for producing STAGs with certain desired properties, selected FAs are incorporated
122 into specific positions of the glycerol backbone (Akanbi and Barrow, 2015; Hita et al., 2009; Muñío et al.,
123 2008; Picq et al., 2013).

124 Enzymatic synthesis of STAGs rich in DHA at *sn*-2 position and CA at *sn*-1,3 positions have already been
125 reported using fish oils. Hita et al. (2007) obtained MLM-STAGs with 45% CA (91% of which was located
126 at *sn*-1,3 positions) and 16% DHA (51% located in *sn*-2 position) from tuna oil through acidolysis reactions
127 using *Rhizopus delemar* lipase as catalyst. Also Sousa et al. (2014) incorporated up to 50 wt% of CA into
128 the TAGs from fish oil, in a solvent-free media, using a 1:2 fish oil/free fatty acid molar ratio, through
129 acidolysis catalyzed by *Thermomyces lanuginosus* lipase (2 wt% of total substrates).

130 Certainly, today, the main source of n-3 PUFAs are fish oils (Finco et al., 2017), but the overexploitation
131 of fishery resources and the growing demand for these oils has led to a search for new and more sustainable
132 sources (Adarme-Vega et al., 2014). Since in fish oils have been detected many harmful compounds (such
133 as mercury and pesticides), influenced by severe marine pollution in recent years, concerns about the safety
134 of fish oil for n-3 PUFAs production have been voiced (Gribble et al., 2016). Krill oil is also an alternative
135 source of n-3 PUFAs that is gaining market share. Its production is based on the fishing of the small
136 crustacean *Euphausia superba*, which lives in Antarctic waters (Burri and Johnsen, 2015) but its
137 overexploitation might be causing serious damage to polar ecosystems as it is a fundamental link in the
138 food chain (Pottel et al., 2014).

139 Thraustochytrids are seen as the most promising alternative to fish oils for human consumption as a
140 nutraceutical, or in animal feed, where DHA oil from Thraustochytrids can replace the use of fishmeal
141 (Aasen et al., 2016; Fossier Marchan et al., 2018; Gupta et al., 2012). Thraustochytrids are heterotrophic
142 marine microorganisms that is closely related to heterokont algae with very high oil content (up to 75% of
143 dry cell weight). The oil is mainly constituted by neutral lipids (NLs) (>80% w/w), it is rich in DHA and
144 has a low cholesterol content (Liu et al., 2014; Morita et al., 2006; Yaguchi et al., 1997). *Aurantiochytrium*
145 *limacinum SR21* (previously known as *Schizochytrium limacinum SR21*) is a member of the
146 Thraustochytrid family (Honda et al., 1998; Yokoyama and Honda, 2007). Previous studies reported that
147 the cultivation of *A. limacinum SR21* under optimized conditions yield up to 62 g dry biomass/L, with 56 %
148 of fatty acids (of biomass dry weight) and 65 % DHA (of total fatty acids) (Huang et al., 2012; Lee Chang
149 et al., 2013). An increasing number of functional food and cosmetic products using thraustochytrid oils
150 have recently been developed recently, due to the status of 'safe-GRAS' for human consumption given by

151 the American Food and Drugs Administration (FDA, 2018) and by the European Commission (European
152 Parliament, 2014).

153 Response surface methodology (RSM) is a combination of mathematical and statistical methods used to
154 determine the effects of different factors on the response variables, which may be affected by one or several
155 of them and their interactions (Gunst et al., 1996). RSM has been widely used in the optimization of
156 reactions for the production of STAGs by different researchers (Bakir et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2010; Linder
157 et al., 2005; Şahin et al., 2006).

158 Therefore, the purpose of this study was to obtain STAGs with high CA content at *sn*-1,3 positions and
159 DHA at *sn*-2 position by acidolysis of CA and *A. limacinum SR21* oil. The influence of the reaction
160 temperature and intensity of treatment (IOT, lipase amount × reaction time/substrate amount) were
161 evaluated by RSM, testing as catalysts two commercial lipases (Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM).
162 The most suitable conditions for the scaling up of the acidolysis reaction were selected. The obtained
163 STAGs were purified and fully characterized.

164

165 **Materials and methods**

166 **Culture of *A. limacinum SR21* and lipid extraction by supercritical CO₂**

167 The DHA rich lipids used in this work were obtained from *Aurantiochytrium limacinum SR21*, a strain
168 purchased to the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) (MYA-1381). The culture was performed in
169 a 2-liters BioFlo 110 bioreactor (New Brunswick Scientific, USA) in the Bioprocess Research Group
170 facilities at the University of Antioquia (Medellín, Colombia). A batch culture was carried out in 1.5 L of
171 sterilized production medium composed of 75 g of glucose and 34.5 g of yeast extract dissolved in a 1:1
172 mixture of natural seawater and distilled water. 3% inoculum was used and prepared according to Patil &
173 Gogate (2015). In this culture pH, temperature and dissolved oxygen concentration were maintained at 7.0,
174 23 °C, and 30%, respectively. The bioreactor was operated until sugar depletion (72 h) and then the biomass
175 was harvested by centrifugation for 15 min at 11088 g (Universal 320R, Hettich centrifuge, Germany). The
176 wet biomass collected was freeze dried until constant weigh (freeze dryer model Sentry 2.0 VirTis, SP
177 scientific, USA). All chemicals used in the culture were of analytical grade.

178 Lipids were extracted from dried biomass by CO₂ supercritical fluid extraction (CO₂-SFE), using a
179 supercritical extractor Speed 2 SFE (Applied Separations, USA), following the method described by Tang
180 et al. (2011) with some modifications. Briefly, 10 g of biomass powder were packed in a stainless extraction

181 vessel along with 10 g of glass beads to increase the biomass-solvent contact area. The lipids were extracted
182 using a CO₂ flow rate of 0.35 kg/h for 1.75 h. The extraction pressure and temperature were 35 MPa and
183 40°C, respectively. The lipid composition of the *A. limacinum* oil is shown in Figure 1. The lipid extraction
184 yield was calculated as the weight percentage of oil respect to dry biomass.

185

186 **Lipases and chemicals**

187 The lipases tested to catalyze the acidolysis reactions were Lipozyme RM-IM from *Rhizomucor miehei* and
188 Lipozyme TL-IM from *Thermomyces lanuginosus*, both kindly donated by Novozymes® (Bagsvaerd,
189 Denmark). Both lipases show 1,3 positional specificity. Lipozyme RM-IM was supplied immobilized on a
190 macroporous anionic exchange resin and Lipozyme TL-IM on granulated silica.

191 Commercial caprylic acid (CA) of 98% purity (Panreac S.A., Barcelona, Spain) was used as acyl donor.

192 The organic solvents used (hexane, chloroform, acetone, methanol, and absolute dry ethanol) were of
193 analytical grade (Panreac S.A., Barcelona, Spain). All reagents used in the analytical determinations were
194 also of analytical grade. The standards nonadecanoic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and the
195 polyunsaturated fatty acid mixture PUFA No 3 (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA) were used for analytical
196 quantifications.

197

198 **Enzymatic synthesis of STAGs**

199 **Acidolysis catalyzed by lipases dispersed in a batch stirred tank reactor**

200 Acidolysis reactions were initially carried out in 2 mL vials sealed with solid caps with PTFE liner and
201 under inert N₂ atmosphere. A typical reaction mixture contained 31 mg of *A. limacinum* SR21 oil (which
202 contains 25 mg of TAGs; Fig. 1), 23.5 mg of CA (6:1 CA/TAG molar ratio) and 7.5 mg of lipase (14.7 wt%
203 of total substrates), suspended in 324 µL of hexane (11.8 mL hexane/g oil). This mixture was incubated at
204 different temperatures (37-56 °C) and agitated in an incubator shaker (Unimax 1010, Heidolph, Germany)
205 at 300 rpm for different reaction times (3-40 h). In this study the reaction time and lipase amount were
206 included in the independent variable intensity of treatment (IOT). This operational variable is defined as
207 (Hita et al., 2007, González Moreno et al., 2004):

208

$$209 \quad IOT = \frac{\text{lipase amount (g)}}{\text{TAG amount (g)}} \times \text{reaction time (h)} \quad [1]$$

210

211 Several works demonstrated that, provided no enzyme deactivation occurs, the reaction time and lipase
212 amount are equivalent variables. Moreover, this variable allows to obtain a simple criterion for scaling up
213 the reaction or changing the reactor type and the operation mode (Camacho Páez et al., 2002, Hita et al.,
214 2007, González Moreno et al., 2004).

215 In this study, the lipase/TAG ratio was kept constant and the reaction time was adjusted, according to the
216 experimental design (section 2.3.2), to modify the IOT value. The reactions were stopped by separation of
217 lipase by centrifugation for 5 min at 5000 g (Mini Spin Plus Eppendorf Ag 22331, Hamburg), and the
218 products were stored at -24°C until analysis.

219

220 **Experimental design**

221 A central composite design with response surface methodology CCD-RSM for the two *sn-1,3* specific
222 lipases tested (Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM) was used to maximize the incorporation of CA at
223 *sn-1,3* positions of TAGs from *A. limacinum* SR21. A 2² factorial design with 2 axial points and 5 replicates
224 of the central point was selected. Based on preliminary studies, intensity of treatment (IOT) and temperature
225 were chosen as factors (independent variables) and CA content (mol%) in STAG as response variable,
226 according to the central composite design (CCD-RSM). In this experimental design there were five coded
227 factor levels: $-\alpha$, -1, 0, +1, $+\alpha$; in which -1 corresponds to the low level of each factor, +1 to the high level,
228 0 to the mid-level and α to the axial points. The levels of the experimental factors are presented in Table
229 1A. All the experiments were carried out by duplicate. The experimental results were fitted with a second-
230 order polynomial equation through a multiple regression technique, using the Design Expert 11.0 software
231 (Stat ease, USA). The regression coefficients were used to make a statistical calculation for further
232 generating 3D surface plots. The models with the optimal conditions were experimentally validated.

233

234 In order to compare the obtained results at the different experimental conditions, Statgraphics centurion
235 XVII software (Statistical Graphics Co., Rockville) was used to carry out the statistical analyses. *P*-values
236 below 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Tukey multiple range test was used to find significantly
237 different average values.

238

239 **Scaling up of the acidolysis reaction**

240 The acidolysis reactions established by RSM models at which high CA incorporations were achieved were
241 analyzed for scaling up (factor X 20). Also, a low temperature and short reaction time were considered to
242 select the scaling up conditions. This scaling up was carried out for both lipases, Lipozyme TL-IM and
243 RM-IM. Reactions were carried out in 50 mL flasks with ground glass stopper, under inert atmosphere and
244 at a stirring speed of 300 rpm. The reaction mixtures consisted of 620 mg of *A. limacinum* oil -containing
245 500 mg of TAGs- 470 mg of commercial CA, 150 mg of lipase, and 6.5 mL of hexane. These mixtures
246 were incubated at 37 °C and agitated in an incubator shaker (Inkubator 1000, Unimax 1010 Heidolph Klein,
247 Germany) at 300 rpm for 30.4 h (Lipozyme TL-IM) or 26.2 h (Lipozyme RM-IM). The reactions were
248 stopped by separation of lipase by filtration (glass plate of porosity 4, Pobel, Spain). Reaction products
249 were fit to a known volume and stored at -24 °C until analysis. All reactions and their corresponding
250 analyses were carried out by duplicate.

251

252 **Purification of structured triacylglycerols (STAG)**

253 In order to separate the acidolysis reaction products (mainly STAGs and free fatty acids, FFAs) contained
254 in the hexane used as reaction medium, a procedure previously developed by Jiménez Callejón et al.
255 (2010b) was implemented. The FFAs contained in the reaction products from the scaled process (49.1 wt%
256 STAG, 50.9 wt% FFAs) were neutralized at room temperature with 12 mL of a KOH-hydroalcoholic
257 solution (1.5:1 molar ratio KOH/FFAs). The FFA moles were calculated considering CA (the major fatty
258 acid) as representative of all fatty acids (molecular weight = 144.2 g/mol). For this, the mixture was
259 intensively agitated and decanted. Next, two phases were separated, an upper hexanic phase containing the
260 purified STAGs and a lower hydroalcoholic phase containing mainly the neutralized FFAs. Then, hexane
261 was evaporated under a nitrogen stream and purified STAGs were analyzed and characterized according to
262 Section 2.4.

263

264 **Analytical procedures**

265

266 **Determination of fatty acid and lipid class composition of *A. limacinum* SR21 oil**

267 Firstly, the total lipids obtained by supercritical CO₂ SFE (Section 2.1) were analyzed by gas
268 chromatography (GC). Aliquots containing approximately 1 mg of lipids in 1 mL of hexane were directly

269 transesterified in presence of 50 μL (2.5 mg/mL) of nonadecanoic acid, which was used as internal standard
270 for the quantitative determination of fatty acids. Transesterification was carried out with acetyl
271 chloride/methanol (1:20 v/v) using the method by Lepage and Roy (1984). 2 μL of methylated sample
272 containing the fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were analyzed by GC in an Agilent Technologies 6890N
273 (Santa Clara, USA) chromatograph, equipped with a capillary column of fused silica OmegaWax™ 250
274 (0.25 mm, 30 m, 0.25 μm standard film, Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) and a flame ionization detector (FID).
275 Nitrogen was the carrier gas at a flow rate of 58.1 mL/min and a split ratio of 1:40. The injector and detector
276 temperatures were set at 250 °C and 260 °C, respectively. The oven temperature was initially set at 150 °C
277 for 3 min, then it was programmed to increase up to 240 °C at a rate of 7.5 °C/min and set at 240 °C for
278 12 min. The fatty acids were determined as FAMES by comparing the retention times against those of
279 the PUFA No. 3 standard, which were analyzed under the same conditions (Jiménez Callejón et al., 2014).
280 This analysis provided the fatty acid composition of total lipids extracted from *A. limacinum* (Fig. 1A).
281 Secondly, the total lipids extracted from *A. limacinum* biomass were also characterized by fractionation
282 into neutral lipids (NLs), glycolipids (GLs) and phospholipids (PLs), following the method described in
283 Jiménez Callejón et al. (2014). 10 mg of *A. limacinum* oil were solubilized in 0.5 mL of chloroform and
284 fractionated in a silica-gel cartridge (Sep-pack plus WAT020520, Waters Corporation, Milford, MA).
285 Samples were eluted with 30 mL of chloroform, 30 mL of acetone along with 20 mL of
286 chloroform/methanol 85:15 v/v, and 30 mL of methanol mobile phases; the NLs, GLs, and PLs fractions
287 were collected from each sample. The transesterification and GC analysis of all fractions, as is described
288 above, gave the percentage of each lipid class and their fatty acid profile. Lipid class composition obtained
289 is described in Section 3.1.

290

291 **Analysis of the reaction products by TLC-GC**

292 The reaction products (mono, di, and triacylglycerols; TAGs; and FFAs) were separated and identified by
293 thin-layer chromatography (TLC) following the procedure described by Hita et al. (2007). The samples
294 (2 mg) were spotted on silica gel plates (Precoated TLC Plates, SIL-G25, Macherey-Nagel, Sigma
295 Aldrich) previously activated by heating at 105 °C for 30 min. The used mobile phase was
296 chloroform/acetone/methanol (95:4.5:0.5 v/v/v). Each one of the lipidic species was visualized by spraying
297 the plate with iodine vapor in a nitrogen stream. The band corresponding to each species was scraped from
298 TLC plates and 1 mL of hexane was added to each sample. 50 μL (2.5 mg/mL) of nonadecanoic acid were

299 used as internal standard. Then, the fatty acids were methylated and quantified by GC following the
300 procedures described in previous articles (Esteban et al., 2011; Hita et al., 2009).

301

302 **Positional distribution of FAs in TAGs and STAGs**

303 The positional distribution of fatty acids in the *A. limacinum* TAGs and STAGs was determined by
304 ethanolysis catalyzed by the lipase Novozym 435 (Robles et al., 2011). In this case, 200 μ L of a hexanic
305 solution with a TAG concentration of 0.25 g/L, 250 μ L of dry absolute ethanol and 25 mg of lipase were
306 used. Under these conditions (using a great excess of ethanol) the lipase Novozym 435 behaves as 1,3
307 specific. The ethanolysis products were analyzed by TLC and GC-FID. TLC was used to separate the 2-
308 monoacylglycerols (2-MAGs) from the reaction products. The 2-MAG band was scrapped off, methylated,
309 and analyzed by GC, as previously described. This analysis provided the fatty acid profile at the *sn*-2
310 position of TAGs and STAGs.

311 From the total content of a given fatty acid (FA_x) in a TAG and the content of this fatty acid at the *sn*-2
312 position, the content of that fatty acid at *sn*-1,3 positions with respect to the total fatty acids at *sn*-1,3
313 positions was calculated using the equation (Esteban et al., 2011):

314

$$315 \quad FA_x \text{ at } sn-1,3 \text{ positions (mol\%)} = \frac{3 \times \% \text{ total content of } FA_x \text{ in TAG} - \% FA_x \text{ at } sn-2 \text{ position}}{2} \quad [2]$$

316

317 The percentages of a determined fatty acid (FA_x) at *sn*-2 and *sn*-1,3 positions, in relation to the total amount
318 of that fatty acid in TAGs, were determined using the equations (Esteban et al., 2011):

319

$$320 \quad \text{Relative content of } FA_x \text{ at } sn-2 \text{ position (mol\%)} = \frac{\% FA_x \text{ at } sn-2 \text{ position}}{3 \times \% \text{ total content of } FA_x \text{ in TAG}} \times 100 \quad [3]$$

321

$$322 \quad \text{Relative content of } FA_x \text{ at } sn-(1,3) \text{ position (mol\%)} = 100 -$$

$$323 \quad \text{Relative content of } FA_x \text{ at } sn-2 \text{ position (mol\%)} \quad [4]$$

324

325 **Results**

326

327 **Extraction and characterization of *A. limacinum* SR21 lipids**

328 The lipid fraction, from *A. limacinum*'s lyophilized biomass, was extracted by CO₂ SFE in the conditions
329 described in Section 2.1. A lipid extraction yield of 35.4 wt% respect to the biomass dry weight was
330 achieved. The fractionation of the *A. limacinum* oil (Section 2.4.1) into NLs, GLs, and PLs indicated that
331 saponifiable lipids (i.e., lipids that contains fatty acids, 95.6 wt%) of this oil contain these lipidic species in
332 the proportions of 92.7, 6.2, and 1.1 wt%, respectively. The TLC-GC analysis of the NL fraction revealed
333 that TAGs are the main component of this fraction (91.0 wt%).

334

335 Figure 1A shows the composition in the main fatty acids of total saponifiable lipids, TAGs, and *sn*-2
336 position of *A. limacinum* TAGs present in the raw extracted oil. This figure shows that the main extracted
337 fatty acids were palmitic acid (PA, 53.0 mol% or 38.3 wt%) and DHA (31.4 mol% or 41.8 wt%), being the
338 *sn*-2 position of TAGs mostly constituted by DHA (49.9 mol%). This implies that 73.1 mol% of total DHA
339 is located at *sn*-2 position (Fig. 1 B, equation [3]) whereas 82.9 mol% of total PA is located at *sn*-1,3
340 positions (Fig. 1B, equation [4]).

341

342 **Acidolysis of *A. limacinum* oil and CA catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM: model**
343 **fitting**

344 STAGs containing DHA, mainly at *sn*-2 position, and medium-chain fatty acids at *sn*-1,3 positions were
345 obtained by acidolysis between *A. limacinum* SR21 saponifiable lipids (mainly TAGs present in the
346 extracted oil) and CA. Following some previous experiments, the chosen variables to be optimized by RSM
347 were the reaction temperature and the IOT (Equation [1]). In this work the lipase/TAG ratio was kept
348 constant; therefore, for modifying the IOT, only the reaction time was considered.

349 Table 1 shows the design matrix of the variables (factors, Table 1A) along with the experimental and
350 predicted response values (CA incorporated to TAGs, Table 1B). The low and high temperature levels (37
351 and 56 °C, Table 1A) were chosen considering a mild operating condition for the lipases and the hexane
352 boiling temperature (68 °C). The IOT range (1.80-10.00, Table 1A) was selected based on previous
353 experiments in which the acidolysis reactions ran until reach a constant CA content (data not shown). Table
354 1B shows that similar CA incorporations were achieved using both lipases, being the experimental CA
355 contents in the range of 22.5-50.1 mol% using Lipozyme TL-IM and 14.5-46.8 mol% using Lipozyme RM-
356 IM.

357 The experimental data (Table 1B) from the acidolysis reactions were fitted to quadratic models for
358 describing the behavior of the system. The quadratic regression analysis was carried out using Design-
359 Expert software, getting the regression equations [5] and [6] for the acidolysis catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-
360 IM and RM-IM, respectively:

361

$$362 \text{ CA content in STAGs (mol\%)} = -3.20 + 1.49 * T + 5.00 * IOT - 0.001 * T * IOT - 0.019 * T^2 - \\ 363 0.27 * IOT^2 \quad [5]$$

364

$$365 \text{ CA content in STAGs (mol\%)} = -16.11 + 1.32 * T + 9.33 * IOT - 0.06 * T * IOT - 0.01 * T^2 - \\ 366 0.39 * IOT^2 \quad [6]$$

367

368 Table 1B shows that the predicted results are comparable to the experimental values, indicating that the
369 design is suitable for optimizations. Quadratic models [5] and [6] were analyzed by analysis of variance
370 (ANOVA) and the results are shown in Table 2. The ANOVA results, for incorporating CA into *A.*
371 *limacinum SR21* saponifiable lipids, showed a model p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.050) for the acidolysis
372 catalyzed by both lipases, which means that the models are statistically significant. The adequate precision
373 value (Table 2) measures the signal to noise ratio; this parameter was much greater than 4 for both lipases
374 (21.03 and 23.79, Table 2). This implies that the signals were adequate for the models used to navigate the
375 design space (Fig. 2). The determination coefficients R^2 (0.9345 and 0.9400 for TL-IM and RM-IM lipases,
376 respectively) were satisfactory in both models, meaning that only around 6% of the experimental results
377 were not explained by the proposed models. The predicted R^2 were in reasonable agreement with the
378 Adjusted R^2 (0.9173 for TL-IM, and 0.9240 for RM-IM). Thus, the regression equations [5] and [6] can be
379 used to analyze and predict the experimental results. Table 2 along equations [5] and [6] show that IOT is
380 the most significant factor on the incorporation of CA to STAGs.

381 Fig. 2 represents the three-dimensional surface response plots generated from the CCD experiments or the
382 representation of the regression models. Figs. 2A and 2C represent the effect of interaction between the two
383 tested variables (temperature and IOT) on the CA incorporation to STAGs, catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM
384 and RM-IM, respectively. These figures show that the CA incorporation increases as the temperature
385 decreases at a constant IOT of 10 g lipase h/g TAG. At low IOT the influence of temperature on the CA

386 content is negligible. Similarly, the CA incorporation increases alongside increases of IOT at a constant
387 temperature of 37°C.

388 Figs. 2B and 2D show that a good correlation is given between the predicted and experimental CA
389 incorporations catalyzed by both lipases.

390

391 The models were verified under the optimal predicted conditions for both enzymes to confirm the validity
392 of the predicted response through four successive experiments. The optimization arguments were a high
393 CA incorporation at the lowest temperature and IOT possible, which was motivated by preserving the
394 PUFA and lipase stability (Fureby et al., 1996; Xu et al., 1998). Table 3 shows the optimal IOTs provided
395 by CCD-RSM at a temperature of 37°C for both lipases, since at this low temperature the maximum CA
396 incorporations were achieved (Figs. 2A and 2C). At this temperature, the optimum IOTs were 9.02 and
397 7.87 g lipase × h/g TAG for Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively, involving reaction times of 30.1 h
398 and 26.2 h (TAG and lipase amounts of 25 and 7.5 mg, respectively). Table 3 shows that the average
399 experimental CA contents reached were 47.3% and 44.6% for Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively.
400 These predicted values from both models (i.e., lipases) were not statistically different from the experimental
401 values ($P < 0.05$). In this way, it was possible to use the models to predict values inside of the experimental
402 space. Lipozyme TL-IM reached a slightly higher CA incorporation into the TAGs from *A. limacinum*
403 SR21 saponifiable lipids, although the optimal IOT was somewhat higher than the required for Lipozyme
404 RM-IM (Table 3).

405

406 **Scaling up of the acidolysis reaction and purification of STAGs**

407 Conditions described in Table 3 were scaled up by multiplying the oil, CA, lipase, and hexane amounts
408 times a factor of 20, maintaining unaltered the IOT (Equation [1]) and, therefore, the reaction times (30.1 h
409 for Lipozyme TL-IM and 26.2 h for Lipozyme RM-IM). Thus, the reaction mixtures consisted of 620 mg
410 of *A. limacinum* oil (containing 500 mg of TAGs), 470 mg of CA, 150 mg of lipase, and 6.5 mL of hexane.
411 Table 4 shows that in the scaled-up conditions, the lipases Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM increased the CA
412 content in TAG up to 40.8 mol% and 39.5 mol%, respectively. The TLC analysis of the STAGs after the
413 purification step, showed that pure STAGs (free of FFAs) were obtained from the acidolysis reaction
414 mixture, with a total average yield of 85% (with respect to STAGs contained in the reaction products). The
415 fatty acid profile of the TAGs remained unchanged before and after purification.

416

417 **Positional analysis of fatty acids in STAG**

418

419 The positional analysis of the STAGs obtained using both lipases showed that, in average, 92 mol% of the
420 total CA incorporated is located at the *sn*-1,3 positions, being the CA content at *sn*-1,3 positions 55.8 and
421 55.1 mol% for Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively (Table 4). Consequently, using, for example,
422 Lipozyme TL-IM as catalyst, the PA content at these *sn*-1,3 positions decreased from 77.3 to 20.4 mol%
423 (decrease of 74%, percentages expressed with respect to total fatty acids in those positions, Table 4A).
424 Using Lipozyme RM-IM, the PA content at *sn*-1,3 positions was reduced to 22.1 mol% (Table 4B), which
425 is a decrease of 73% of PA contained in these extreme positions. DHA content at the *sn*-2 position was 45.5
426 and 45.9 mol% for Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively, so, 59.2 and 63.9 mol% of total DHA was
427 located at *sn*-2 position for both lipases (Table 4). Acyl-migration values (CA incorporated at the *sn*-2
428 position) of 10.8 mol% for Lipozyme TL-IM and 8.4 mol% for Lipozyme RM-IM were obtained.

429

430 **Discussion**

431

432 **Extraction and characterization of *A. limacinum* SR21 lipids**

433 Oil extraction yield from *A. limacinum* SR21 biomass obtained in this work (35.4 wt%) is similar to the
434 one reached by other authors, 33.7 wt% (He et al., 2017) or 33.9 wt% (Tang et al., 2011) using CO₂ SFE.
435 Likewise, oil extracted also showed a lipidic profile (92.7, 6.2 and 1.1 wt% of NLs, GLs and PLs,
436 respectively, with TAGs as main component), analogous to those commonly reported for Thraustochytrid
437 species. So for example, a 95.9 wt% of the total fatty acids of *Schizochytrium magnrovei* were NLs, of
438 which TAGs were the predominant lipid fraction (97.2 wt% of total fatty acids) (Fan et al., 2007). In
439 addition, the main fatty acids extracted in this work were PA (53.0 mol% or 38.3 wt%) and DHA
440 (31.4 mol% or 41.8 wt%). Similar results were found by Ling et al. (2015) from *Schizochytrium sp.* LU310
441 (40.0 wt% PA and 40.9 wt% DHA) or Chen et al. (2016) from *Schizochytrium sp.* S056 (40.6 wt% PA and
442 39.7 wt% DHA). However, lower DHA contents were observed by Tang et al. (2011a) and He et al. (2017b)
443 in oil extraction from *A. limacinum* biomass (27.5 and 35.2 wt%, respectively). At the same time, the high
444 relative content of DHA at *sn*-2 position (73.2 mol%, Fig. 1 B) and of saturated fatty acids at *sn*-1,3
445 positions (82.92 mol% of total PA, Fig. 1 B) makes this oil suitable to produce STAGs highly rich in DHA
446 at the central position and a medium-chain fatty acid, as caprylic acid (CA), at the *sn*-1,3 positions by

447 acidolysis catalyzed by a regioselective (1,3 specific) lipase. These CA-DHA-CA STAGs provide DHA
448 which is later absorbed as DHA 2-MAG by the human digestive system. The CA contained in this structure
449 is also absorbed and does not have the side effects of the long chain saturated fatty acids at *sn*-1,3 positions
450 (Wei et al., 2019), which are presents in the original TAG.

451

452 **Acidolysis of *A. limacinum* oil and CA catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM: model**
453 **fitting, scaling up and purification of STAGs**

454 Temperature, lipase/substrate ratio and reaction time are the most critical factors for attaining high
455 conversions by acidolysis of *A. limacinum* oil and CA (Jennings and Akoh, 1999; Mu et al., 1998; Wang et
456 al., 2012). With respect to the CA/TAG molar ratio, a constant value of 6/1 was kept constant in this work,
457 similarly to Hita et al. (2007, 2009) and Kim et al. (2002) in the acidolysis of CA and perilla oil catalyzed
458 by Lipozyme TL IM and RM IM. This molar ratio is in the range 2:1-8:1, which is commonly used in these
459 acidolysis reactions, because higher ratios showed little or no increase in incorporation. High molar ratios
460 can improve the reaction rate, shorten the reaction time, increase the TAGs conversion to STAGs and
461 reduce the acyl-migration; nevertheless, the separation of FFAs and STAGs after the acidolysis reaction
462 can be more difficult (Mu et al., 1998). Hexane was used as reaction medium in order to reduce the
463 viscosity, increase the solubility of nonpolar substrates and shift the reaction toward synthesis rather than
464 hydrolysis (Klibanov, 1986). In this way, González Moreno et al. (2004) found that, without solvent, the
465 acidolysis reaction rate of an EPA-enriched oil and CA decreased when the substrate concentration
466 increased due to the high viscosity of the reaction mixture (in the high concentration range). Kim et al.
467 (2002) also achieved higher incorporation of CA to TAGs of perilla oil in hexane against solvent free
468 medium using Lipozyme TL-IM (51.4 versus 30.6 mol%) and Lipozyme RM-IM (48.5 versus 34.2 mol%).
469 The maximum experimental CA contents obtained in this work with both lipases, 50.1 mol% using
470 Lipozyme TL-IM and 46.8 mol% using Lipozyme RM-IM, are similar to the ones achieved by Hita et al.
471 (2007) in the acidolysis of tuna oil (20% DHA) and CA, catalyzed by *Rhizopus delemar* lipase immobilized
472 on Accurel MP1000. In this work, a maximum CA content of 45.2-51.0 mol% was attained. Furthermore,
473 39.3-53.0 mol% of CA in TAGs was obtained in a similar acidolysis reaction catalyzed by the lipase
474 Palatase 20000L (Hita et al., 2009).

475 The experimental data from the acidolysis reactions were fitted to quadratic models (equations [5] and [6])
476 for describing the behavior of the system and the determination coefficients R^2 (0.9345 and 0.9400 for TL-

477 IM and RM-IM lipases, respectively) were satisfactory in both models (only around 6% of the experimental
478 results were not explained by the proposed models). Taking this into account, the three-dimensional surface
479 response plots generated from the CCD experiments (representation of the regression models, Fig. 2) allows
480 to obtain a good estimation of the maximum CA incorporations, 49.7 ± 2.2 mol% for Lipozyme TL-IM and
481 46.8 ± 2.4 mol% for Lipozyme RM-IM, respectively (Figs. 2A and 2C and Table 3). Figs. 2A and 2C also
482 show that at high IOTs the CA incorporation tends to be constant, which could indicate that equilibrium
483 has been reached. Hita et al. (2007) evaluated the IOT in a range of 0-5.03 g lipase·h/g TAG in the acidolysis
484 of tuna oil (rich in DHA) and CA catalyzed by immobilized *Rhizopus delemar* lipase; in that work, a yield
485 of 56% of CA incorporated to TAG was obtained at IOT of 2.01 g·h/g; at this IOT, the equilibrium was
486 also attained in the conditions used in that work.

487 However, the CA incorporations obtained in the scaling up of the acidolysis reaction (40.8 mol% using
488 Lipozyme TL-IM and 39.5 mol% using RM-IM) were lower than the ones predicted either by the models
489 or the experiments at the smaller scale (Table 3). This could be caused by the geometric shape of the
490 reaction containers. In the scale-up experiment, the observed turbulence rate on the acidolysis was lower
491 when compared to the smaller scale experiment. This less contact between the substrates and the enzyme
492 can decrease the incorporation of CA to the TAGs. For this reason, maintaining constant the stirring rate
493 (300 rpm) with a higher reaction mixture volume is probably not a correct criterion to maintain the mass
494 transfer rate constant, and therefore, the apparent reaction velocity, considering that the lipase is contained
495 in a solid phase (Vikbjerg et al., 2005).

496 After purifying the reaction mixture obtained in the scaled reaction, pure STAGs were obtained with a yield
497 of 85% (with respect to STAGs contained in the reaction products). This yield was a little higher than the
498 one obtained by Hita et al. (2007), 80%, in the separation of DHA rich STAGs (from tuna oil) and CA rich
499 FFAs using the same purification procedure. These yields are not higher because, in presence of high FFA
500 contents, a relatively high percentage of STAGs remain in the hydroalcoholic phase, emulsified by the great
501 amounts of formed soaps.

502

503 **Positional analysis of fatty acids in STAG**

504 The positional distribution of fatty acids in STAGs obtained in this work shows that the PA content at *sn*-
505 1,3 positions decreased significantly compared with the initial extracted oil. Using for example, Lipozyme
506 TL-IM as catalyst, a decrease from 77.3 to 20.4 mol% was observed (Table 4A). This result improves

507 considerably the applicability of the obtained STAG as nutraceutical, since a saturated long chain fatty acid,
508 PA (16:0), is replaced by a medium chain fatty acid, CA (8:0), which is much easier to absorb by the human
509 organism. On the other hand, DHA content at the *sn*-2 position decreased slightly from 49.9% in the original
510 oil to 45.5 and 45.9 mol% after acidolysis reaction with Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively. This
511 small decrease could be due to the acyl-migration (Wang et al., 2012, Mu et al., 1998), because, since both
512 lipases are *sn*-1,3 specific, the fatty acid composition at the *sn*-2 position should have remained unaltered.
513 The acyl-migration values (CA incorporated at the *sn*-2 position) obtained (10.8 mol% for Lipozyme TL-
514 IM and 8.4 mol% for Lipozyme RM-IM) were similar to those obtained by other authors (Table 5). For
515 example Wang et al., (2012) obtained acyl-migration values of 11.5 and 9.7 mol% in the acidolysis of CA
516 and canola oil catalyzed by the same lipases used in this work, Lipozyme TL-IM and RM-IM, respectively.
517 Acyl-migration increases with reaction time and temperature and it is catalyzed, for example, by solids with
518 superficial charge (Egger et al., 1997; Svensson et al., 1992). In this regards, Lipozyme RM-IM uses an
519 anion exchange resin as lipase carrier, which catalyzes acyl migration (Araújo et al., 2016). In any case,
520 this positional analysis shows that the predominant type of obtained STAG has the structure MLM, with
521 CA as the medium chain fatty acid, M, and DHA as the long-chain fatty acid, L.

522 All in all, similar results were obtained using both lipases in this work. The same was observed by Kim et
523 al., (2002) for the incorporation of CA to perilla oil (Table 5). Nevertheless, Lipozyme TL-M is much
524 cheaper than Lipozyme RM-IM (800 \$USD/Kg vs. 8000 \$USD/Kg, Strem chemicals, 2020), which
525 reinforces the selection of Lipozyme TL-IM as catalyst to obtain DHA rich STAG by acidolysis of *A.*
526 *limacinum* oil and CA.

527

528 **Conclusions**

529 *A. limacinum* SR21 saponifiable lipids contain 92.7 wt% of neutral lipids, most of which (91 wt%) are
530 TAGs. This oil contains a 31.4 mol% of DHA (41.9 wt%), with 73.1 mol% of this DHA at *sn*-2 position of
531 TAGs. This lipidic composition makes this oil suitable for obtaining STAGs, highly rich in DHA at *sn*-2
532 position and CA at *sn*-1,3 positions, by acidolysis of the oil and CA catalyzed by *sn*-1,3 specific lipases,
533 such as Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM. A central composite design for optimizing the most
534 important variables of the acidolysis reaction (temperature and IOT) allowed to obtain two statistical
535 models (one for each of the tested lipases) that are able to predict the CA incorporation in the obtained
536 STAGs ($R^2 > 0.91$). The incorporation of CA increases the nutritional value given that CA displaced,

537 fundamentally, the palmitic acid at *sn*-1,3 positions. Thus, using Lipozyme TL-IM at the optimized
538 conditions (37°C and an IOT of 9.02 g lipase h/g TAG), the PA content at *sn*-1,3 positions decreased from
539 77.3 mol%, in the original oil, to 20.4 mol%, while CA content in those positions increased from zero to
540 55.8 mol%. The obtained STAGs contain 25.6% DHA, which constitutes 45.5 mol% of total fatty acids
541 located at *sn*-2 position. The optimal conditions and composition for the obtained STAGs using Lipozyme
542 RM-IM as catalyst were similar to the ones obtained using Lipozyme TL-IM.

543

544 **Declarations**

545 **Funding**

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548 **Conflicts of interest**

549 The manuscript was prepared and reviewed with the participation of all authors, who declare that there is
550 no conflict of interest that jeopardizes the validity of the presented results.

551

Figure 1. Characterization of *A. limacinum* SR21 oil: (A) Fatty acids composition (mol%) of total lipids (determined by direct GC), TAGs (determined by TLC-GC) and sn-2 position of TAGs (determined by ethanolysis with Novozym 435 followed by TLC-GC). (B) Relative content of fatty acids (mol%) located at sn-2 and sn-1,3 positions of TAGs (equations [3] and [4], respectively)

552

Table 1. Central composite design (CCD) for acidolysis reactions between *A. limacinum* SR21 oil and caprylic acid (CA) catalyzed by lipases Lipozyme TL-IM and Lipozyme RM-IM.

A. Range and levels of independent variables at five coded levels.

Variables	Coding	Units	Levels				
			- α	-1	0	+1	+ α
Temperature	A	°C	33.06	37.00	46.50	56.00	59.94
IOT	B	g lipase x h/g TAG	0.10	1.80	5.90	10.00	11.70
Response	Name	Units					
CA content in TAGs	CA content	Mol %					

553

B. Experimental (Exp.) and predicted (Pred.) responses (CA content in TAGs, mol%).

Run	A	B	Lipase TL-IM		Lipase RM-IM	
			Essay 1	Essay 2	Essay 1	Essay 2
			Exp./Pred.	Exp./Pred.	Exp./Pred.	Exp./Pred.
1	33.0	5.9	44.96 / 45.57	44.77 / 46.08	43.29 / 43.56	43.68 / 42.77
2	46.5	11.7	50.13 / 47.35	50.98 / 47.86	41.99 / 40.79	39.05 / 40.00
3	37.0	1.8	37.75 / 34.10	36.71 / 34.61	27.71 / 26.89	27.87 / 26.11
4	59.9	5.9	39.37 / 38.76	40.18 / 39.27	33.13 / 37.16	34.07 / 36.38
5	56.0	10.0	42.44 / 44.65	42.03 / 45.16	39.68 / 38.37	39.41 / 37.58
6	46.5	5.9	44.79 / 45.56	46.51 / 46.07	43.64 / 42.71	40.72 / 41.93
7	46.5	0.1	22.51 / 25.63	22.94 / 26.14	14.50 / 18.17	15.09 / 17.38
8	46.5	5.9	45.29 / 45.56	46.41 / 46.07	42.23 / 42.71	43.44 / 41.93
9	56.0	1.8	32.22 / 29.19	29.98 / 29.70	30.20 / 26.95	30.43 / 26.16
10	46.5	5.9	45.45 / 45.56	45.62 / 46.07	43.68 / 42.71	42.83 / 41.93
11	46.5	5.9	45.25 / 45.56	45.91 / 46.07	43.65 / 42.71	37.44 / 41.93
12	46.5	5.9	45.94 / 45.56	47.02 / 46.07	43.57 / 42.71	42.00 / 41.93
13	37.0	10.0	46.33 / 49.37	50.02 / 49.88	45.64 / 47.46	46.68 / 46.68

554 *Operational conditions:* 31 mg of *A. limacinum* oil (containing 25 mg of TAGs), 23.5 mg CA, and 7.5 mg
 555 lipase suspended in 324 μ L of hexane, agitated at 300 rpm.
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Table 2. ANOVA results for quadratic models for the acidolysis reactions catalyzed by: (a) Lipozyme TL-IM and (b) Lipozyme RM-IM.

a.				
Source	Sum of	df	Mean	p-value
Block	1.69	1	1.69	
Model	1340.61	5	268.12	0.000
A-Temperature	92.85	1	92.85	0.000
B-IOT	943.94	1	943.94	0.000
AB	0.02	1	0.02	0.951
A ²	40.15	1	40.15	0.010
B ²	286.46	1	286.46	0.000
Residual	93.90	19	4.94	
Lack of Fit	92.03	11	8.37	0.000
Pure Error	1.87	8	0.23	
Cor. Total	1436.20	25		
Std. Dev.	2.22		R ²	0.9345
C.V. %	5.30		Adjusted R ²	0.9173
Adeq. Precision	21.03			
b.				
Block	4.02	1	4.02	
Model	1757.62	5	351.52	0.000
A-Temperature	81.76	1	81.76	0.001
B-IOT	1023.22	1	1023.22	0.000
AB	41.82	1	41.82	0.016
A ²	19.24	1	19.24	0.088
B ²	609.44	1	609.44	0.000
Residual	112.87	19	5.94	
Lack of Fit	88.65	11	8.06	0.088
Pure Error	24.22	8	3.03	
Cor. Total	1874.52	25		

Std. Dev.	2.44	R ²	0.940
C.V. %	6.50	Adjusted R ²	0.924
Adeq. Precision	23.79		

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Figure 2. Surface response plots of the factor's effect on CA content in STAGs: The effect of interactions between IOT and temperature on acidolysis catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM (A) and Lipozyme RM-IM (C). The correlation plot of predicted values vs experimental measurements for acidolysis catalyzed by Lipozyme TL-IM (B) and Lipozyme RM-IM (D).
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572 Table 3. Validation of the models and optimization of results
 CCD-RSM optimized conditions

Factors.	Lipozyme TL-IM	Lipozyme RM-IM
A.	37	37
B.	9,02	7,87
Mol% content of CA in STAG		
Model Prediction	49.7 ± 2.2 ^a	46.8 ± 2.4 ^{a,b}
95% PI low	46.8	44.1
95% PI high	52.6	49.6
Exp. Results*	47.3 ± 1.1 ^a	44.6 ± 0.6 ^b

*Mean ± SD (n= 6). Means for each value sharing the same uppercase letter in each column and row are not significantly different as indicated by Duncan's multiple range test (P < 0.05).

573 *Operational conditions:* 31 mg of *A. limacinum* oil (containing 25 mg of TAGs), 23.5 mg CA, and 7.5 mg
 574 lipase suspended in 324 µL of hexane, agitated at 300 rpm.
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577

578

579 Table 4. Scaling up of the optimized conditions for the acidolysis reactions; fatty acid composition (mol%)
 580 of STAGs obtained after purification step.

A. Lipozyme TL-IM

Fatty acid	STAGs	<i>Sn</i> -2 position	<i>Sn</i> -1,3 positions ^a	Relative content at <i>sn</i> -2 position ^b	Relative content at <i>sn</i> -1,3 positions ^c
8:0	40.8 ± 0.8	10.8 ± 1	55.8 ± 1.8	8.8 ± 1	91.2 ± 1
14:0	3.2 ± 0.2	5.5 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.3	57.5 ± 4.4	42.5 ± 4.4
16:0	21.7 ± 0.7	24.3 ± 0.4	20.4 ± 1.2	37.3 ± 1.9	62.7 ± 1.9
16:1 ω 7	0.3 ± 0.2	-	0.4 ± 0.2	-	100 ± 0
16:3 ω 4	0.7 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	37.4 ± 3.0	62.6 ± 3.1
18:1 ω 9	0.8 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	41.9 ± 4.2	58.1 ± 4.2
18:4 ω 3	2.5 ± 0.1	-	3.7 ± 0.1	-	100 ± 0
20:1 ω 9	0.2 ± 0.1	-	0.2 ± 0.1	-	100 ± 0
22:5 ω 6	4.3 ± 0.1	8.6 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.2	66.9 ± 1.6	33.1 ± 1.6
22:6 ω 3	25.7 ± 0.2	45.5 ± 0.6	15.7 ± 0.8	59.2 ± 1.3	40.8 ± 1.3

B. Lipozyme RM-IM

8:0	39.5 ± 0.4	8.4 ± 0.6	55.1 ± 0.1	7.1 ± 0.6	92.9 ± 0.6
14:0	3.6 ± 0.1	6.9 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.3	64.8 ± 3.1	35.2 ± 3.1
16:0	24.4 ± 0.2	28.9 ± 0.3	22.1 ± 0.8	39.5 ± 1.1	60.5 ± 1.1
16:1 ω 7	0.3 ± 0.1	-	0.5 ± 0.1	-	100 ± 0
16:3 ω 4	0.8 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	40.0 ± 5.6	60.0 ± 5.6
18:1 ω 9	0.9 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	41.9 ± 4.6	58.1 ± 4.6
18:4 ω 3	2.4 ± 0.1	-	3.6 ± 0.1	-	100 ± 0
20:1 ω 9	0.2 ± 0.1	-	0.3 ± 0.1	-	100 ± 0
22:5 ω 6	4.0 ± 0.1	8.5 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	71.7 ± 1.0	28.3 ± 1.0
22:6 ω 3	23.9 ± 0.2	45.9 ± 0.2	13.0 ± 0.4	63.9 ± 0.7	36.1 ± 0.7

^a equation [2]; ^b equation [3]; ^c equation [4].

Operational conditions: 620 mg of *A. limacinum* oil (containing 500 mg of TAGs), 470 mg CA, and 150 mg lipase suspended in 6.5 mL of hexane, agitated at 300 rpm.

Table 5. Comparison between the results obtained in this and other works about DHA and CA contents and their distribution in STAGs.

Substrates and lipase	Fatty acid	STAG	Sn-2 position	Sn-1,3 positions	Reference
<i>A. limacinum</i> SR21 oil, CA, and Lipozyme TL-IM	DHA CA	25.7 40.8	45.5 10.8	15.7 55.8	this study
<i>A. limacinum</i> SR21 oil, CA, and Lipozyme RM-IM	DHA CA	23.9 39.5	45.9 8.4	13.0 55.1	this study
Tuna oil, CA, and <i>Rhizopus delemar</i> lipase	DHA CA	16.2 45.2	24.9 12.8	11.9 61.4	Hita et al., 2007
Tuna oil, CA, and Palatase 20.000L	DHA CA	17.5 39.3	42.1 7.1	5.2 55.5	Hita et al., 2009
DHA single cell oil, CA*, and <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	DHA CA*	37.1 10.2	39.9 5.6	35.7 16.9	Hamam and Shahidi, 2004
TAGs with high EPA and DHA content and CA	DHA CA	23.5 43.0	52.6 11.5	9.0 58.8	Jennings and Akoh, 1999
Canola oil, CA, and Lipozyme RM-IM	LA, LnA ^a CA	17.8 45.3	36.1 9.7	8.7 63.1	Wang et al., 2012
Perilla oil, CA, and Lipozyme TL-IM	LA, LnA ^a CA	35.7 51.4	71.0 10.7	18.1 71.8	Kim et al., 2002
Perilla oil, CA, and Lipozyme RM IM	LA, LnA ^a CA	39.3 48.5	75.0 7.1	21.5 69.2	Kim et al., 2002

581 CA*, capric Acid; LA, linoleic acid (18:2); LnA^a, linolenic acid (18:3).

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